

THE IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATION IN ECONOMIC GROWTH.

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Annotation; The article discusses the productivity disparity between developed and developing countries since the 1970s, attributing it to differences in capital intensity and qualifications. Despite a strong scientific foundation, there is a notable weakness in technological innovations in developing nations, reflected in low R&D, patents, and a lag in adopting advanced practices. The document emphasizes technological innovation as a key driver of economic growth, exploring the concept of "uncertainty" in the search for new technologies and its impact on both developed and developing economies.

Key words: Innovations, science, technology, economic growth, technovation.

Introduction.

Innovation and technological progress are important factors in economic growth, as they increase the level of technology available in the economy, leading to an increase in overall output at the macroeconomic level. Technological innovation has been an important factor in economic growth throughout history. From the industrial revolution to the digital age, technological innovations have transformed the global economy and improved people's lives. Technological innovation was associated with increased productivity, high living standards, and economic prosperity.

Technological progress is the main driver of sustainable economic growth in the long term and should contribute to changing the path of economic growth. Technological innovation and the introduction of technology are the two main modes of technological progress, but the role of technological innovation and the application of technology in the way of economic growth is small. For example, some scientists study the impact of independent innovation on general factor indicators, some scientists study the impact of technology implementation on general factor indicators or the impact of input and output speed to determine the impact of technological innovation. To assess the impact of the application of technology on changing the way economic growth occurs, but the ratio of total productivity and cost of production factors cannot accurately reflect the mode of economic growth from wide changes to intensive changes, so the results of these studies do not need to be justified. When the rate of economic growth is positive,

an increase in the overall productivity of the factors of production does not create sufficient conditions for the entry and exit rates, which intuitively may reflect the economic norm, but the conditions necessary for the growth of the level of economic growth, but production is the result of the interaction between the factors of production, the ratio of factors of production to total productivity or product cost does not reflect the impact of technological innovation and the application of technology in changing the way economic growth occurs. The introduction of innovations and technologies to change the path of economic growth, which is not only of considerable theoretical importance, but also helps to change the path of economic growth on the path of technological development so that valid proposals can be made. The main innovation of this article: theory reveals technological innovation and the application of technology to transform the path of economic growth into a function of uncertainty; application of technology to study technological innovation and change the function of change in the path of economic growth; use the method of evaluation of empirical research of simulating innovations for economic growth at the level of intensive evaluation to establish technological innovation and promote the transformation of the path of economic growth into technological innovation with the participation of foreign capital of multiplier type.

As mentioned above, although the concept of innovation is somewhat difficult to define, it can be considered that there are three forms: (1) cost reduction, (2) quality improvement and (3) expansion of the range of goods, services and production methods. Innovation is the search for new and better ways of doing business and bringing new ideas or new types of products and services to market.

This focus on “new ways of doing things”[1] and “the development and widespread adoption of new kinds of products, production processes, services, and business and organizational models”[2] is what lies at the heart of the process of innovation. But what is crucial about this process is that it serves as a means to an end: it helps drive progress, and human flourishing more generally. “Innovation is more than the latest technology,” notes Sofia Ranchordás, a resident fellow at the Yale Law School. “It is a phenomenon that can result in the improvement of living conditions of people and strengthening of communities. Innovation can be technological and social, and the former might assist the latter to empower groups in ways we once thought unimaginable.”[3]

Methodology

Therefore, the purpose of this article is to review the available empirical literature on technological innovations and their impact on developing countries. To achieve this, the author thoroughly studied the literature and documentary information on the subject of the study. As for, the article is based solely on the methodology of studying desktop computers and libraries. In this article, we will conduct a study using empirical methods based on existing research. In this sense, in the process of preparing this study, selected articles, scientific papers and diagnostic research reports from leading business journals were analyzed. By evaluating the evidence quantitatively or percentally qualitatively, the researcher can answer empirical questions that must be clearly defined and supported by the evidence collected (usually called data). The design of the studio varies depending on the field and silver under study. The review focuses primarily on technological research conducted around the world from 2005 to the present.

Understanding the concept of Technovation-the article covers all aspects of the process of technological innovation, from conceptualizing a new product or process based on technology to commercial use. Topics include technological trends and discoveries that support innovation, the availability of capital for the development and introduction of new products, the relocation of existing products, the management of entrepreneurial enterprises, the management of innovations in medium and large organizations, organizational structures intended for the development of innovations, investment strategies related to the new science- technology-based enterprises, as an innovator person and as a personality type, and technology transfer to developing countries [4] as well as case studies showing how innovation occurs from a business and engineering perspective, as well as reviewing and analyzing government and industrial policies that hinder or encourage technological progress. innovation. Innovation should be understood as something new for the local context. This relativism with respect to context is important and especially relevant for developing countries. From a Global point of view, three forms of innovation can be distinguished. The first refers to local improvements based on the introduction of technologies that are more or less available globally or locally ("technology adoption" from a global perspective). The second type of innovation is expressed in the growth of competitive activity with a certain adaptation ("technological adaptation") to existing technologies. The third type of innovation is the development and production of technologies of global importance ("technological creation" from a global point of view) [5]

This section presents empirical research on innovations around the world and the company's activities in the industry. The focus is on highlighting existing research findings and conclusions that are useful in determining research outcomes. According to the 2015 edition of the United Nations, any effective Global Partnership that supports Inclusive Development should define development as a common goal for all. The relevance of interrelated issues, such as technology and innovation, requires a balance of priorities and concerns worldwide to achieve an uncompetitive paradigm shift. Such a new global agreement will need new ideas backed by effective policies and tools to provide a roadmap for action and impact. It is necessary to discuss whether a limited set of goals helps to achieve this goal. In addition to its role in the provision of global public goods, science, technology and innovation (IT) serve as an important factor in improving national well-being and competitiveness. However since the technological knowledge and skills were total, the first advantages of moving created a very uneven global landscape. Linking local technological needs with international technological capabilities is a particular challenge for many developing countries. The problem identified in this review of alternative concepts of innovation is that innovation is unattainable and should not be ignored, but many existing concepts and direct daily observations, at best, give the innovation process only a limited perspective. This is probably not surprising, but it confirms the conclusion made in the first part of the chapter: If the general concept is an object, then a broad concept of technological change is appropriate. It follows that the rest of this study should be devoted to analyzing the variability of elements of a broad definition of technology. Changes in technology affect innovation and cluster problems. The "Push technology suggestion" suggests that this approach, well known in the literature, is determined not by the need for the opposite direction and the level of technological change, but by the use of a special industry [6] and technological compliance. The advantages of copying technologies in countries in the early stages of development are that their entrepreneurs can concentrate on ensuring new improvements to foreign projects, instead of focusing on the dangerous development of new products and technologies for the world.

This is an innovative process that is new for the local market or the national company, but new for everyone. After the onset of rapid growth, a gradual transition, in the most successful countries, to innovation at the beginning of knowledge. In many ways, it is the history (and the current function) of technological innovation and development in developed countries. There are

many changes in the scientific and technical policy of the OECD. The OECD can contribute to the dissemination of best policy practices among Member States. Currently, work is underway to assess the links between science and industry in several OECD countries. This allows a better understanding of the main barriers affecting the role of science in innovation and helps to improve policies in OECD member countries. In 2001, the OECD's work on economic growth culminated in a comprehensive report presented to ministers, which includes a series of policy recommendations (Technovation) on the role of Science, Technology and innovation in economic growth. Efforts to develop more accurate indicators of scientific and technical progress, especially in areas related to the new economy, lead to a better understanding of the roots of economic growth and social change. He shows in his research that most technological changes in underdeveloped countries, in most cases, consist of adapting imported technologies to the local environment and delivery factors.[7] The diffusion of innovation occurs through a series of communication channels between members of a similar social system in a given period. However, this indicates that the introduction of innovations takes place within the framework of a five-step process. The five steps or stages are knowledge:

- persuasion
- decision
- implementation
- confirmation.

In his study, he empirically concluded that Britain had improved relative productivity since 1970, but there is still a significant difference in market sector productivity between the UK and continental European countries, the US and Africa. A significant part of the gap between Britain and continental Europe is due to low capital intensity and skills. However, there is still a significant difference between the UK and the US, even if they are taken into account. These gaps cover all sectors and reflect not only vulnerability in high-tech sectors, but also the inability to implement advanced technologies and skills in large segments of the market sector. The main reasons here are competition in the market of low-end OS products, regulation of the market of high-end OS products, and the general absence of the use of advanced methods and technologies. Part of this story is the weakness of technological innovation, despite the high-quality scientific base. Technological innovations are growing and spreading year after year in many developed countries, and many clusters involved have recognized improvements. In developing countries there is a gap

that needs to be filled in order to invest in technological innovation. This includes a relatively low and declining rate of R & D and patents, as well as a significant lag in the spread of innovation.

Discussions of Results from the Review

"Accelerated technological change has become a fact and will continue to challenge industrial and societal development in this new century." Anticipating these changes seems to be crucial for success in technologybased companies. For Technovation these changes have two sides: on the one side, the Technology is an object of change and on the other side, it is subject to change. As an object of change the Innovation has to adapt quickly to new environments [8]. This requires a high degree of flexibility and sensitivity due to their limited resources. Employees and the organization must be open to new ideas and implement them quickly, since they cannot rely on unlimited financial resources and often work in small innovative markets. Technological innovation around the world is one of the driving forces of productivity growth. However, it is difficult to argue that technological innovations or their absence in the economy are an important factor explaining the changes over the past fifty years. The history of unemployment/inflation has the weakest connection with technological progress. Even significant fluctuations in per capita productivity and GDP compared to other countries are due not to technological innovations, but to the degree to which advanced companies use best practices. Of course, they are closely related to technology, but the main problem is much more organizational than a technological feature. And the main problems are related to the promotion of the use of best practices and obstacles along the way. These are, of course, serious issues that we will indirectly discuss in the future. Here we focused on the role of technological innovation, although it was inevitable; it led us to talk about how to use innovation. As we can see, relative productivity indicators in developed countries have improved over the past twenty years, especially taking into account production. During this period, technological growth was one of the highest in these countries. Establishing links between knowledge gathering and business development is one of the most important challenges facing developing countries. There are many ways in which governments can promote the development of small and medium-sized enterprises; for example, by supporting business incubators and technology centers, export processing zones and production networks that allow small enterprises to integrate business services and labor. To create and support enterprises that contribute to sustainable development, special tax regimes and

market instruments are needed, as well as a wide range of financial capital emission strategies. Actions that contribute to the achievement of sustainable development Goals are carried out at all spatial levels, from international framework agreements to national policies and action plans, decisions and behaviors of local communities, families and individuals. Governments, businesses and industries, as well as a wide range of civil society organizations are taking action. For this reason, there is a need for broad mechanisms to inform and influence actions carried out at these different levels and by different groups of actors. For example, at the international level, scientific and technical communities need to constantly participate in intergovernmental ministerial conferences, while decisions at the local and individual levels can be more effectively justified through long-term commitments to strengthen educational programs and institutions. These mechanisms should evolve over time in accordance with the changing overall agenda for the use of science and technology for sustainable development.

Conclusion and Implications

Technologies in developing countries face difficulties due to a lack of sufficient funds (capital), because their organizations are still innovative, and also because they are in a rapidly changing environment. For successful technological management in these conditions, the management system must be compact, flexible and adaptable. The concept of Pocket (Pocket Technology Management or Technology and Innovation Management) is aimed at providing support according to the needs of your company, opportunities and beneficiaries. To compete with big competitors, companies based on new technologies need to develop advantages such as flexibility and responsiveness. To take advantage of these advantages, NTBF requires a technology and innovation management approach that enhances NTBF's competitive advantages in dozens of business organizations, fast communication, and intelligent decision-making mechanisms. However, almost all research in the field of technology and innovation management was conducted in large companies, so in a different context. Technological innovations play an important role in the whole range of themes described in the previous chapters, and are highlighted here for their fundamental importance for short-and long-term economic, social and environmental sustainability. Technological innovation can be seen as a double-edged sword in relation to sustainable development. There is no doubt that much of the improvement in human well-being in the last century can be attributed to technological innovations in areas such as public health and

agriculture. But at the same time, many of the most important problems of sustainable development in the world are the unintended consequences of technological developments, especially those aimed at increasing the production and extraction of natural resources.

Literature:

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